

Reference sheet for the publication:

Towards sensor agnostic artificial intelligence for underwater imagery

Publication home:

[IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters](#) (24 April 2023)

DOI: [10.1109/UT49729.2023.10103403](https://doi.org/10.1109/UT49729.2023.10103403)

Description:

Underwater images in global datasets are gathered by different cameras and under different lighting and altitude conditions. Image formation models can potentially compensate for these known differences and improve machine learning (ML) performance. In this paper we will investigate how ML trained on images from one system can classify images taken by another. We will train two ML classification models based on two different underwater camera systems. We are going to evaluate the performance of each model with data from both platforms and will demonstrate the improvement of using image formation models to make an image look-like it has been gathered with a different system and how ML performance is affected.

Data sharing:

Green Open Access, currently embargoed but available to those with access to IEEE Xplore. For more information please contact comms.techoceans@aquatt.ie.

Archiving and preservation (including storage and backup):

At the end of the embargo period the full publication will be archived under this Zenodo entry.

